

UNDERSTANDING VOLTAGE AND CURRENT DISTRIBUTION OF COST EFFECTIVE CARBON COMPOSITE TEST SAMPLES FOR AIRCRAFT LIGHTNING STRIKE TESTS

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ABSTRACT

Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) materials are now used extensively in aircraft structures. They can be designed to match the mechanical performance of aluminum but with lower weight, leading to reduced fuel consumption and lower emissions. Statistically, an aircraft is struck by lightning every ten thousand hours of flight. For this reason, it must be protected from damage that could occur because of the lightning attachment impact and current flow through the aircraft structure.

Lightning tests must be performed in order to understand the different aspects of a lightning strike event and for the development of efficient protection systems. Aircraft lightning tests are expensive because of the cost and time related to the manufacture of representative test specimens, especially when considering the large quantity of test samples required for good statistical results. From this perspective, there is a desire to develop more cost effective test samples. However to enable this, it is first necessary to increase understanding of the distribution of electrical potential and current within a test sample when subjected to a lightning strike.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are extensively used in aerospace industries [1]. CFRP has been used since the 1960s in military aircraft and from the 1970s in civil aviation for small parts, but it is in the last few decades that they have been employed even for primary load carrying structures [2]. The main reason to use CFRP is for a better strength-to-weight ratio compared to conventional metal, leading to a lower weight of the aircraft. This can have significant cost savings for airline companies because of lower fuel consumption and, more importantly, benefit the environment because of associated lower emissions. Nowadays, the aviation CO₂ emission is estimated to be 1.6% of the global Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions. However, according to the Stern Review, it can be as high as 2.5% of the global GHG emissions in 2050 [3].

CFRP material for the aerospace industry is usually fabricated in a laminated form that is a stack of thin plies (0.125 – 0.250 mm). Each ply is made of fibres that can be carbon, Kevlar or glass, all in the same direction embedded in a matrix, usually epoxy. By laying different plies in different directions, one on top of the other, it is possible to create CFRP laminates that have a tailored strength and stiffness, e.g. strengthening of the property by directing the fibres in the same direction as the main stress.

Aerospace materials need to match not only specific mechanical characteristics but also suitable electrical and thermal properties need to be achieved. A significant threat for an aircraft is a lightning strike in flight. A flash can deliver from tens to hundreds of kiloAmperes of current to the aircraft structures, and if not suitably protected, it may lead to serious damage like melting, puncture, burning (direct effects) but also interference with the electronic equipment of the aircraft due to electromagnetic coupling to the lightning strike channel (indirect effects) [4].

Current flow in CFRP differs to conventional aluminium due to the significant differences in the electrical properties. Unlike for metals, the layered material structure of CFRP restricts the uniform distribution of current within the bulk of the material when struck by lightning. This paper presents a study of the current and potential distributions within a simple geometry made by a circular CFRP

panel with a fastener at its centre, defining the current injection location. Fasteners are usually used in aerospace applications to join different parts of the structure together, e.g. joining the wing skin with the underlying spar/rib. Lightning can attach to the surface of the skin or to the head of one fastener which allows the lightning current to flow through it into other aircraft structures. Many tests need to be performed in order to understand and develop protection systems that minimise damage and threat due to this type of current conduction. The lightning tests are expensive because of the cost and time related to the manufacture of representative test samples, especially when complex geometries are involved or if there is a desire to perform statistical experiments that require many test specimens. Therefore, there is a need to develop more cost effective test samples. In order to enable this, it is necessary to develop a good knowledge of the materials, their electrical properties and the conduction mechanism within these structures.

An approach that utilises numerical simulation was adopted for this study since it allows for a high level of freedom in terms of sample design and parametric simulations. Furthermore, it allows examination of test scenarios and configurations that are prohibitively expensive or just cannot be achieved with physical experiments.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE SIMULATED EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

To illustrate the current flow and its distribution within a ply, Figure 1 shows a simple case of current injection into a single unidirectional ply from a point (single fibre in this case) as indicated by the arrow on the left hand side of the figure. As a consequence of the fibres touching each other within each ply, the current spreads into adjacent fibres through the contact regions between fibres. This allows a better uniformity of the current distribution on the right hand side of the test sample, hence helps reducing the current density. In this case, the contact points between the fibres help to improve the conductivity in the transverse direction. In cross section A, close to the injection point, the current path does not cover the entire cross section of the test sample, resulting in a current density shape similar to that shown in Figure 2a. In contrast, in cross section B close to the ground side, the same current flows over a wider section of the test sample giving a current density distribution similar to that shown in Figure 2b.

Figure 1: Current spreading in a unidirectional ply

Figure 2: Current density magnitude normalized for cross sections A and B

The experimental set up that is currently used to investigate the direct effects of lightning strikes on aircraft materials and components is modelled in COMSOL with the aim to determine the impact of the test parameters and circuit elements on the test results. The simulation model and programme consisted of a series of electromagnetic simulations, where a DC current of 200 A magnitude was injected into the test sample and collected through a grounding system. The test sample was made by a stack of 4 plies, each 0.25 mm thick, of circular shape with the orientation [45/135/90/0]. A fastener,

where the current was injected, is located at its centre. For different sizes of the test object and for different electrical properties of the composite panel, the simulation results help to visualise and analyse the electrical parameters within each ply of the panel for different configurations of the grounding system. Physical measurements of the electrical parameters, such as potential and current distributions in the individual plies of the panel, are not yet achievable in the laboratory. However, numerical simulations allow a high degree of freedom in terms of sample design and testing (parametric study). The variables investigated were: voltage drop between the injection fastener and the ground point and current distribution within each ply of the panel.

Three model parameters, (grounding system, contact impedance between plies and radius of the panel), were tested using parametric simulations in order to understand their impact in the electrical characteristics as described above. The radius of the panel and the grounding system affect the cost of the materials and the cost of manufacturing the test sample. Three different radii were chosen in order to quantify the impact of the test panel dimensions: 50, 100, 150 mm radius. The grounding system forces the current to flow through particular paths within the panel, modifying in some cases the electrical properties of the test sample. Two main grounding scenarios were used for this simulation:

- *Grounding with fasteners*
 - *Grounding with one pair of diametrically-opposed side fasteners (Scenario 2f)*: involves a pair of fasteners located on the sample perimeter on opposite sides of the central fastener. This is used in order to establish a symmetrical distribution of potential/current near the central fastener. It forces the current to flow to specific ground sinks (the grounding fasteners), modifying the distribution of potential/current within the panel compared with the side grounding scenario. This scenario also modifies the geometry of the test sample as the grounding fasteners are fitted in holes which excludes parts of the CFRP panel during the conduction process, i.e. substituted with the metal fasteners and the CFRP material beyond the outer fasteners (Figure 3a).
 - *Grounding with multiple pairs of diametrically-opposed side fasteners*: Each pair of fasteners is positioned on the sample circumference diametrically-opposed at 10 mm from the border of the panel. In addition to the one pair scenario described above where the pair of fasteners were aligned with ply 0°, four other scenarios were studied using multiple pairs: 2 pairs of fasteners (Scenario 4f) aligned with 0° and 90° plies (Figure 3b), 4 pairs of fasteners (Scenario 8f) aligned with 0°, 45°, 90° and 135° plies sequentially (Figure 3c) and then rotated by 22.5° (Figure 3d) which makes the fasteners not aligned with any of the plies (Scenario 8f_r), and finally, 6 pairs of fasteners (Scenario 12f) aligned in sequence with 0°, 30°, 60°, 90°, 120° and 150° (Figure 3e).
- *Side grounding (Scenario side)*: this consists of grounding the entire panel perimeter edge. It creates a continuous grounding boundary around the panel which then allows the current to distribute within the panel according to available conduction paths. However, it should be noted that it does not modify the geometry of the panel (Figure 3f).

Figure 3: Grounding systems: (a) 2 fasteners, (b) 4 fasteners, (c) 8 fasteners, (d) 8 fasteners rotated, (e) 12 fasteners, (f) side

The alignment between the direction of the ply and the fasteners pairs facilitates, under specific conditions, the current to flow through a highly conductive path between the injection fastener and the grounding fasteners within the ply. This reduces the current density uniformity in the panel. To improve the uniformity of the current distribution in the test panel, another configuration with 8 grounding fasteners was used. The rotation of these by 22.5° maintains the symmetry of the current/potential distribution within the panel. The fastener configuration with 6 pairs of fasteners is a mix between aligned and not aligned grounding configurations.

Between any two adjacent plies in the composite panel, there is an interlamina surface which is located at the interface between the two plies. In some materials, this interface layer is composed predominantly of resin. However, it is recognised that contact spots between fibres of the two adjacent plies can be present at this interface. Such contact acts like a distributed impedance, thus, allowing the current to flow between plies through the contact spots of the fibres. During the manufacturing process of the CFRP material, there are several parameters such as curing temperature, curing pressure and the ply lay-up that can influence the characteristics of the interface and, consequently, the associated electrical characteristics [5]. It is quite difficult to carry out a physical measurement of the conductivity of the interlamina surface but it is important, for an accurate numerical model, to understand how this unknown variable impacts on the current/potential distribution.

For this reason, a parametric simulation was carried out, using four conductivities for interlamina centred resistance: 100, 2.4, 0.1 and 0.01 S/m. Each ply was modelled using an orthotropic conductivity matrix where $\sigma_f=20000$ S/m (conductivity along the fibres), $\sigma_t=100$ S/m (conductivity transverse fibres) and $\sigma_{tt}=100$ S/m (conductivity through thickness). The three values have been measured through a procedure amenable to the experiment of Todoroki A. [6]. A similar set of values can be found in the work of Cheng J. [7]. This gives the following conductivity matrix:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_f & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_t & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sigma_{tt} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 20000 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 100 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 100 \end{pmatrix} \text{ S/m} \quad (1)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Potential

When a current of 200 A DC is injected, Figure 4 shows the voltage drop between the central injection fastener and ground electrode, which is always held at 0 V. These results indicate the variation of the terminal resistance seen from the source for the various scenarios and interface layer conductivity.

Figure 4: Voltage drop across the test sample for a 200A injection for various grounding scenarios for four interlamina conductivities of a 50 mm radius sample.

Each group shows a different grounding arrangement starting from the *2 fasteners* grounding to the *side* grounding. Within each group, the columns show the voltage drop for different contact impedances. The behaviour in common for all the grounding configurations is that decreasing the conductivity between plies increases the voltage drop. The decrease of the interlamina conductivity forces the current to flow in highly resistive paths within the panel to reach the ground, and this increases the voltage drop. For higher conductivities (91 – 2.4 S/m), the voltage drop is independent from all the grounding scenarios, except for the *2 fasteners* arrangement (Scenario *2f*). Higher interlamina conductivities allow the current to move freely between plies flowing in low resistivity paths within the sample and the grounding scenario does not affect appreciably the current path.

Grounding Scenarios *2f*, *4f*, *8f* show a decrease of voltage drop for lower conductivities (0.1 – 0.01 S/m) and with increasing the number of fasteners. In these first three cases, the fasteners pairs are always aligned with the main directions of the plies which correspond to highly conductive paths (HCP) between the injection fastener and the grounding fasteners. In the *2 fasteners* case, the HCP is in ply 0°, and the current injected in that ply flows through a low resistance path. However, in the other three plies, the current must spread in the transverse direction of the fibres to reach the grounding point. In the case of the *4f* scenario, there are two HCPs, one in ply 0° and the other in ply 90°. In the *8f* scenario case, there is a HCP in each ply allowing the current in each ply can flow through a low resistance path. Increasing the number of grounding fasteners, aligned with the plies, the injected current flows in more low resistance paths, and this contributes to a decrease of the total voltage drop.

The *side* grounding scenario shows a voltage drop magnitude that is close to that of the *8 fasteners* grounding scenario except for the 0.01 S/m conductivity case where the voltage drop of the *side* grounding is slightly higher (13 % higher). For both cases, the current can flow through low resistance paths within all the plies but the difference in voltage drop can be found analysing the length of the current paths. In the *8f* grounding scenario, the gap between the injection fasteners and the grounding fasteners is less than 40 mm whereas, in the *side* grounding scenario, it is 50 mm from the central fastener to the side. The increase of 35% of that length can be related with the increase of the voltage drop in the *side* grounding. The *8f rotated* scenario was designed to avoid HCP and enhance the spreading of the current in the transverse way of the fibres. In this case, the 0.01 S/m conductivity shows the highest voltage drop as the current cannot flow between plies and it cannot move just along the fibres. To reach the fasteners forming the ground electrodes, the current must flow in the transverse direction encountering higher resistivity paths and, consequently, higher voltage drop.

The voltage drops related to the 100 – 150 mm panels show the same trends but with increased magnitudes due to longer current paths between injection and grounding points. As expected, the *side* grounding scenario shows the lowest voltage drop compared with the other five grounding scenarios for both sample sizes.

3.2 Current density

Figure 5 shows the current density distribution within ply 0° for the six grounding systems and for two interlamina conductivities: 100 S/m and 0.01 S/m. Considering the A row, it can be clearly seen that the current flows along the direction of the fibres. The presence of a symmetry line of the current distribution that is in the opposite direction of the fibres can confirm the symmetry of the current distribution. For the *2f* – *4f* – *8f* – *12f* scenarios, the current flow is enhanced in a strip between the injection fastener and the fastener pair aligned with 0° oriented ply. Most of the current within the ply is thus collected by that fastener pair. This effect is attributed to two main reasons: (a) the lowest resistivity of the ply is in the 0° direction, and the current does not need to flow in transverse direction to reach the ground, and (b) the high electrical insulation between plies does not allow the current to flow between them.

Scenario *8f rotated* was investigated to restrict current flow avoiding low conductivity path along the fibre direction in all plies, this is designed to obtain a more homogenous distribution of the current but comparatively a highly resistive path. From the computed pattern, it can be seen that the high current density strip is still present but the magnitude is decreased. The current tends to spread to reach the ground and all the grounding fasteners are involved in sharing the current flow. The *side* grounding scenario provides a smoother current distribution compared with other scenarios.

Figure 5: Current density distribution within ply 0° for six grounding scenarios:
A) 0.01 S/m B) 100 S/m interlamina conductivity

The B row shows the case of the interlamina conductivity equal to the transverse conductivity (100 S/m). In this case, the current still flows in the direction of the fibres maintaining the symmetry but it can also flow through the thickness direction more than case A. This leads to an improvement of the current distribution within each ply for all the grounding configurations.

Analysing the other three plies of the test panel, it is possible to distinguish the following: in scenarios *8f*, *8f rotated* and *side* grounding, the current density distributions within plies 90° 135° and 45° are similar to those of ply 0° but rotated with the equivalent angles of the plies (Figure 6). In the *2f scenario*, the other three plies did not have a pair of grounding fasteners aligned with them, and the current of those plies flow in the transverse directions to reach the ground fasteners. The grounding system is not matched with the entire panel but just with one ply. For the *4f* and *12f* scenarios, the grounding systems are matched with ply 0° and ply 90°. The current distribution is similar but rotated just for those two plies exhibiting similar patterns as the previous case.

Figure 6: Current density distribution within ply 45° for six grounding scenarios using
0.01 S/m interlamina conductivity

4 CONCLUSIONS

The simulations performed in this work have quantified the influence of the interlamina conductivity and the grounding system on the electrical parameters of a CFRP panel.

The side grounding arrangement can be considered the ‘ideal’ grounding because it allows the current to flow through the sample freely, similar to a larger sample, and there is no influence from fasteners. The objective is to obtain a practical grounding system with a current distribution sufficiently close to the ideal case with the minimum of complexity and cost.

The fastener arrangement influences the current distribution when using a fastener grounding configuration. It has been noted that the increase of the fastener pairs improves the current distribution,

approaching the case of side grounding. Also the position of the fastener pairs has a strong influence. Aligning the fasteners with the fibres reduces the current distribution by introducing low resistance paths. The fastener grounding arrangements require that each sample is drilled in order to install the grounding fasteners.

It has been shown that the influence of the grounding system depends on the interlamina conductivity of the CFRP. The simulations have shown that higher interlamina conductivity values allow a better current flow through the thickness of the panel, improving the current distribution within the test panel. Higher values of interlamina conductivity have contributed to decrease the average resistance of the panel, leading to a lower voltage drop between the injection fastener and the grounding system. Also, higher interlamina conductivities were shown to help the current flow in lower resistivity paths, leading to a further reduction of the voltage drop. For higher interlamina conductivity values the change in grounding scenarios does not appreciably affect the current distribution. Lower conductivity values increase the insulation between plies preventing the through thickness current flow. This makes the current distribution much more dependent on the grounding configuration.

5 FUTURE WORKS

This study is the first part of the development of test samples to represent more complex aircraft geometries for lightning tests. These tests are expensive partly because of the cost of the test samples and the objective of the study is to enable the design of samples that are more cost effective. Future tasks will include the development of metrics that can be used in trade-off studies that balance achieving an ideal current distribution with the cost of manufacturing a sample.

6 REFERENCES

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